

Microfinance as facilitator for achieving the SDGs: A Systematic Literature Review

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Abstract: The objective of this research is to verify how microfinance can help achieve the SDGs. The objective is pursued through a systematic analysis of the literature and by answering the two identified research questions. The article uses a structured review of international literature through the Scopus database to identify articles and subsequently the analysis is carried out using MySRL and Bibliometrix software. After having analyzed the content of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals, with particular attention to inclusive finance and microfinance, the systematic analysis of the literature highlights how important sustainability is for microfinance. To the extent of our knowledge, we did not find any systematic literature review addressing this topic.

Keywords: Microfinance, SDGs, Financial Inclusion, Sustainability.

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1. Introduction

Microfinance is a financial innovation that has transformed the global economy, offering growth opportunities and economic support to millions of people worldwide and helping reduce poverty, promote enterprise, and stimulate sustainable development. Microfinance provides financial and non-financial services to individuals or groups without access to such services from traditional financial institutions such as banks. The recipients are low-income earners and financially disadvantaged individuals as women. Microfinance is one way to attain financial inclusion, in particular, financial inclusion is an objective while microfinance is a way or method. Microfinance includes microcredit, saving programs, financial payment facilitation, micropension and microinsurance schemes, and remittance facilitation (Gatto, 2021).

Microfinance has a significant positive relationship with developing microbusinesses, reducing inequalities, tackling poverty, fighting socio-economic imbalance, and addressing injustice and weak institutions, which are central to the ideals of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as declared by the United Nations (Manpreet A. and Swati S., 2022). The SDGs comprise 17 ambitious goals included in the 2030 Agenda developed by the United Nations on September 25, 2015 (United Nations, 2015). Access to finance and – most importantly – access to microfinance, emerge today as primary needs and effective strategies for embarking on sustainable development (Gatto A. and Sadik-Zada E.R, 2022). The first Sustainable Development Goal is ENDING EXTREME POVERTY, which explicitly mentions the importance of access to financial services. This goal contains five related objectives by 2030, the fourth one is to ensure that the poor and vulnerable people have equal rights and access to basic services such as microfinance services, appropriate new technology, and natural resources by 2030 (Dzuljastri

A. R. and Qosdan D., 2020). When people are included in the financial system, they are better able to climb out of poverty by investing in business or education. Microfinance helps low-income people create and develop income-generating businesses, improving their living standards and reducing poverty.

Financial inclusion of farmers can unleash bigger investments in the planting season. The results are higher yields and progress toward greater FOOD SECURITY, thus helping to achieve SDG n. 2.

Financial inclusion can encourage GOOD HEALTH, SDG n. 3. Out-of-pocket healthcare costs are an important reason why people are stuck in poverty.

SDG n. 4 promotes QUALITY EDUCATION, but achieving quality education depends on people having the ability to invest in learning opportunities (Klapper L. et al., 2016). On this, researchers have found that small and short-term loans, commitment products, and direct debt services can help households pay expenses (Morduch, 2007).

Increasing account ownership would promote GENDER EQUALITY, SDG n. 5. Microfinance is often aimed at women, as they have greater difficulty accessing traditional financial services. Offering women access to microcredit can improve their economic independence and decision-making power within their families and communities.

Two of the SDGs focus on access to essential infrastructure and resources: WATER AND SANITATION - SDG n.6 - and ENERGY - SDG n.7. Both goals are likely to have a significant impact on people's quality of life. According to the United Nations, today 844 million people do not have access to clean water, and the consequence is the onset of health problems. The World Energy Outlook 2022 states that about 775 million people lack access to electricity, while the availability of energy can improve working conditions and provide greater access to education and health services. Microfinance could help low-income people get clean water and electricity, increasing productivity and their standard of living.

The 2030 Agenda, among their SDGs, also strives to achieve DECENT WORK AND

ECONOMIC GROWTH, SDG n. 8. With these targets in mind, the goal is to achieve full and productive employment and decent work for all women and men through promoting entrepreneurship and enhancing employment opportunities for the poor and microentrepreneurs (Dzuljastri A. R. and Qosdan D., 2020).

SDG n. 9, which calls for BUSINESS INNOVATION, might be served by wider access to credit. Particularly, promoting innovation and sustainable industrialization requires easy access to credit and other financial services that facilitate investment (Klapper L. et al., 2016). The WorldBank Enterprise Surveys state that many firms have limited access to financial services, and this represents one of their main constraint to growth.

Concerning Sustainable Development Goal number 10, REDUCED INEQUALITIES, the United Nations included income inequality as part of the global agenda to improve and transform people, representing a significant factor in achieving sustainable economic development.

The links between financial inclusion and other SDGs are not as well established. Promoting

PEACE AND JUSTICE - SDG n. 16 - is easier when people are economically successful, but it would not be easy to show that financial services can have a strong impact on their own. SDGs not covered at all include goals n. 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 17 (Klapper L. et al., 2016). Given the link between financial inclusion and SDGs, governments should keep pushing for more access to and use of financial services. Prioritizing financial services does not take away resources from other priorities set through the SDGs. The evidence gathered to date builds a strong case that financial inclusion helps create the conditions that bring many of the SDGs within reach.

This paper is organized as follows: after this Introduction there will be Methodology and Results, finally the Conclusion.

Figure 1: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), UN.

2. Methodology

The analysis of the role of microcredit in achieving the SDGs was conducted through a *Systematic Literature Review* (SLR), a literature analysis methodology widely used in the economic field (Massaro et al., 2016). The literature review conducted with a systematic approach allows us to obtain an organic and complete picture of the state of the art regarding a given research topic, as well as to identify possible directions for future research (Snyder, 2019). At the same time, the systematic approach involves the respect of specific guidelines and principles aimed at making the research transparent and replicable, so that the analysis

is as objective as possible (Tranfield et al., 2003).

In this sense, the study conducted follows the PRISMA² methodology, which takes shape in the following steps:

1. Formulation of research questions;
2. Location of studios;
3. Selection and evaluation;
4. Analysis and synthesis;
5. Reporting and results.

In particular, the research questions underlying the study are the following:

RQ1: What are the main topics and future directions of research on the topic concerning the relationship between microcredit and the fight against poverty?

RQ2: What is the role of microcredit in combating poverty?

The SLR conducted is based on the documents present in the Scopus database. The choice derives from the fact that Scopus is the most used database in the academic field and this allows you to have a complete picture of the literature, also guaranteeing a high quality of the documents.

Concerning the selection and evaluation process, to provide an organic picture of the literature, no time constraints were placed, despite having identified the optimal *keywords*, and their best combination and having applied the exclusion/inclusion criterion relating to the subject area. Only the articles were then taken into consideration, regarding the type of document. In this way, it is guaranteed that the documents considered are of high quality. Regarding the language, the analysis was limited to documents in English only. The choice derives from the fact that English allows for more easily comparable documents, also from a textual point of view. Regarding the subject area, the analysis was limited to the areas: Business; Management and Accounting; Social Science; Economics; Econometrics and Finance. This allows to have a sample consistent with the scope of the literature review and allows to consider both empirical and theoretical studies, in order to have as complete a picture as possible of the methodologies used by the scientific community. Using the MySLR software (Ammirato et al., 2022), the documents were manually evaluated on the basis of the title and abstract and, when these were not sufficient, the evaluation was carried out on the basis of the full text.

In particular, the keywords used were microfinance AND SDGs OR sustainability AND poverty OR sustainability AND social AND development. In total, the documents initially identified were 301. Filters relating to the subject area, language and type of document were applied, limiting the search only to articles written in English and relating to the areas: Social Science; Economics; Econometrics and Finance; Business; Management and Accounting. The articles selected after applying the filter were 186.

The document selection process is summarized in Table 1:

Tab. 1: PRISMA methodology, Source: Our elaboration

² Prisma Statement. (2021), “Prisma Transparent Reporting of Systematic Reviews and Meta Analysis”, available at:<http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

The analysis phase was conducted with MySLR and Bibliometrix Software. The use of the two platforms is particularly useful in conducting a Systematic Literature Review, especially with reference to the presentation of the results, since the graphs and tables allow readers to immediately and clearly understand the results. In this sense, a bibliometric analysis was conducted in order to have information on the scientific production of the topic and identify the driving topics, with the aim of highlighting future directions of research.

3. Results

To answer *RQ2*, we conducted a bibliometric analysis on the 186 articles, using the Bibliometrix software, concerned: the annual scientific production; the average citation per year; the keywords; trend topics (thematic map). The choice to focus on scientific production in general terms, without considering the analysis of the authors, derives from the desire to focus attention on the topic and possible future developments of the research.

Regarding the annual scientific production, Figure 2 shows a growing interest of the scientific community in the topic of microfinance, with a strong increase in the production of documents especially between 2020 and 2022.

Figure 2: Annual scientific production

Growing production is accompanied by a reduction in annual citations, which reach, as can be seen from Figure 3, a peak in 2011.

Figure 3: Average citations by year

However, textual analysis shows a prevalence of the term sustainability, second only to microfinance. The relevance of the term sustainability is of particular interest because it denotes particular attention towards sustainability understood from a social profile. In this sense, microfinance as a tool to combat poverty contributes to the achievement of an adequate standard of living and social development, especially in less developed countries. (Tehulu, 2021).

Figure 4: Most relevant terms

The thematic map, constructed as in Figure 5, allows to identify: the motor themes, i.e. the well- developed and relevant themes for structuring the conceptual framework of the domain; the basic themes, significant for the domain and transversal to its different areas; peripheral topics, i.e. topics in decline or in an emerging phase, which are not fully developed or marginally interesting for the domain; niche topics, highly developed but still marginal in the reference framework.

In this specific case, the attention of the scientific community towards emerging economies, in particular Asia, Africa and India, is interesting. Future research could therefore explore the relationship between microfinance and poverty by focusing mainly on emerging countries.

Figure 5: Thematic map

To address RQ1, an analysis was conducted on the 32 selected documents using the PRISMA methodology. In this regard, confirming what was highlighted in the thematic map, a pronounced interest emerges in:

a) Developing Countries

Concerning this first research stream, Montgomery and Weiss (2011) conducted an analysis on data from 3000 borrower and non-borrower households in Pakistan. They found that a commercially- oriented microfinance approach contributed to improving some social indicators, such as those related to health and primary goods expenses, especially in rural areas. Hermes and Lensink (2011) highlighted both the benefits and criticisms of

microfinance, emphasizing that certain customer categories are considered excessively risky, even by microfinance banks. Adjei et al. (2009) noted the contribution of microfinance institutions to the economic growth of poor families in Ghana, particularly in education and health expenses. However, they also highlighted the challenges faced by clients experiencing reduced interest rates over time. García-Pérez et al. (2020) underscored the connection between sustainable development and the specific region where microfinance institutions operate, emphasizing the need to adapt operations to the regional context.

b) Sustainability and Efficiency of Microfinance Institutions

Regarding the second identified stream, Annim (2012) argued that there is a trade-off between the social objectives of MFIs and their financial efficiency. Hermes and Lensink (2011) pointed out the high costs of microfinance programs due to transaction costs. Various theoretical approaches explain the trade-off between sustainability and outreach of microfinance institutions. Tavanti (2013) focused on the strategies adopted by microfinance institutions, suggesting an approach that integrates microfinance into community development. Aslam et al. (2019) concentrated on the trade-off between financial sustainability and social objectives, emphasizing the significant relationship between social and financial performance.

c) Women Empowerment

The theme of gender equality in income opportunities provided by microfinance, while underdeveloped, is present. Warnecke (2015) highlighted the connection between gender equality and economic growth, especially in developing countries, where microfinance plays an essential role in providing income opportunities for women. Pakkanna et al. (2020) emphasized the significant role of women's cooperatives in microfinance in rural areas, impacting women's empowerment differently based on social, cultural, demographic, and geographic factors. Yadav and Verma (2017) showed how reducing the economic opportunity gap between men and women is linked to economic development. Microfinance contributes positively to per capita GDP and human development indicators, improving women's social conditions. Milgram (2001) analyzed a microfinance program in the Philippines, revealing a focus on financial self-sufficiency rather than

social development. The study suggested additional strategies beyond credit provision by microfinance institutions.

Below is a summary schema of the considered articles.

Article	Author	Year
Microfinance: its impact, outreach, and sustainability	Hermes, Lensink	2011
Microcredit and the Poorest of the Poor: Theory and Evidence from Bolivia	Navajas et al.	2000
Banking for the poor: the role of Islamic banking in microfinance initiatives	Dusuki	2008
Can Commercially-oriented Microfinance Help Meet the Millennium Development Goals? Evidence from Pakistan	Montgomery and Weis	2011
Microfinance Efficiency: Trade-Offs and Complementarities between the Objectives of Microfinance Institutions and Their Performance Perspectives	Annim	2012
The challenge of rural financial inclusion –evidence from microfinance	Lopez and Winkler	2018
Before Microfinance: The Social Value of Microsavings in Vincentian Poverty Reduction	Tavanti	2012
Enhancing Climate Change Resilience Through Microfinance: Redefining the Climate Finance Paradigm to Promote Inclusive Growth in Africa	Chirambo	2017
ASSET BUILDING AND POVERTY REDUCTION IN GHANA: THE CASE OF MICROFINANCE	Adjei et al	2009
A poverty outreach index and its application to microfinance	Julia Paxton	2003
Microfinance Institutions Fostering Sustainable Development by Region	Iciar García-Pérez et a	2020
Rural microfinance sustainability: Does local wisdom driven - governance work?	Atahau et al.	2020
MICROFINANCE NORTH AND SOUTH: CONTRASTING CURRENT DEBATES	JOHNSON*	1998
"Greening" Gender Equity: Microfinance and the Sustainable Development Agenda	Tonia Warnecke	2015
Profitability vs Poverty alleviation: has banking logic influences Islamic microfinance institutions?	Luqyan Tamanni	2019
Economy of Mutuality: Merging Financial and Social Sustainability	Kevin T. Jackson	2016
Microfinance for poverty alleviation: Do transnational initiatives overlook fundamental questions of competition and intermediation?	Arp et al.	2017
Does microcredit increase aspirational hope? Evidence from a group lending scheme in Sierra Leone	Garcia et al.	2020
Measuring total factor productivity change of microfinance institutions in India using Malmquist productivity index	Singh et a.	2018
Social Role of Microfinance Institutions in Poverty Eradication: Evidence from ASEAN-5 Countries	Zainal et al.	2019
Interest-free microfinance in India: a case study of Bait-un-Nasr Urban Cooperative Credit Society	Waheed	2019
Microfinance and Poverty 1. Poverty Reduction and Microfinance – Assessing Performance	Greeley	2003
Micro-finance and Poverty Alleviation: Experience of the Rural Poor in Pakistan	Mustafa	2000
Social Versus Financial Performance of Microfinance: Bangladesh Perspective	Aslam et al.	2019
What drives microfinance institution lending behavior? Empirical evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa	Tehulu	2021
The impact of microfinance on poverty and income inequality in developing countries	Subramaniam et al.	2021
Global Financial Partnerships in Microfinance: India, Peru and Tanzania	Marr and Tubaro	2012
Are You Poor Enough? Client Selection by Microfinance Institutions	Wright and Dondo	2023
IS VILLAGE-LEVEL MICROFINANCE BENEFICIAL AT THE COMMUNITY, ENTERPRISE AND HOUSEHOLD LEVELS? A CASE STUDY FROM INDONESIA	Rifai et al.	2021
Microfinance Institutions And Women Empowerment: Evidence In The Rural Areas Of Tangerang, Indonesia	Pakkanna et al.	2020
Microfinance: Driving Empowerment of Women	Yadav and Verma	2017
Operationalizing Microfinance: Women and Craftwork in Ifugao, Upland Philippines	Milgram	2001

Figure 6: Articles included

4. Conclusions

This article examines the role of microfinance in pursuing the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In particular, the purpose of the study is to answer the two research questions formulated, through a systematic analysis of the literature.

Regarding the first research question, microfinance, especially in developing countries, helps fight poverty and more. Access to finance may contribute to a long-lasting increase in income using a rise in investments in income-generating activities and to a possible diversification of sources of income; it may contribute to an accumulation of assets; it may smooth consumption; it may reduce the vulnerability due to illness, drought, and crop failures, and it may contribute to better education,

health and housing of the borrower. In addition, access to finance may contribute to an improvement in the social and economic situation of women (Hermes N. and Lensink R., 2011). The positive contribution brought by inclusive finance, and therefore by microfinance and microcredit in the nations most in need of help, emerged from the analysis of the content of the individual SDGs.

Regarding the second research question, from the analysis of the results of the systematic literature review, it emerged that between 2020 and 2022 there was an increase in the production of papers regarding this research topic. From figure 2, a continuous increase in the production of papers is predicted. It is expected that the main future topics will be those studying microfinance in emerging countries such as Asia and Africa.

For further research, it would be appropriate to consider and carry out a study on the institutions that grant credit and on the possible policies that can be implemented in order to grant credit in a simple way. There is also an urgent need for greater transparency from these institutions which could be constructive for all stakeholders, for private sector investments and for the international donor community.

References

- Adjei, Joseph Kimos & Arun, Thankom. (2009). *Microfinance Programmes and the Poor: Whom Are They Reaching? Evidence from Ghana*. BWPI, The University of Manchester, Brooks World Poverty Institute Working Paper Series.
- Ammirato, S., Felicetti, A.M., Rogano, D. Linzalone, R., Corvello, V. (2022) – “Digitalizing the Systematic Literature Review process: the MySLR platform”, *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*, DOI: 10.1080/14778238.2022.204L•1375; Vol.: ahead-of-print, n°: ahead-of-print.
- Annim, S. *Microfinance Efficiency: Trade-Offs and Complementarities between the Objectives of Microfinance Institutions and Their Performance Perspectives*. *Eur J Dev Res* 24, 788–807 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1057/ejdr.2011.60>
- Aslam, Mohammad & Kumar, Senthil & Sorooshian, Shahryar. (2019). *Impact of Microfinance on Poverty: Qualitative Analysis for Grameen Bank Borrowers*. *International Journal of Financial Research*. 11. 49. 10.5430/ijfr.v11n1p49.
- Banerjee A., Duflo E., Glennerster R., Kinnan C. (2015). *The Miracle of Microfinance? Evidence from Randomized Evaluation*. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, pp. 22-53.
- Barboza G., Trejos S. (2009). *Micro Credit in Chiapas, Mexico: Poverty Reduction Through Group Lending*. *Journal of Business Ethics*, pp. 283–299.
- Dzuljastri, A. R., Qosdan, D. (2020) *Achieving sustainable development goals through microfinance in four selected countries: issues and challenges*. *Journal of Islamic Management Studies*, Vol.3 N.1, pp.1-15.
- García-Pérez, Iciar, María Ángeles Fernández-Izquierdo, and María Jesús Muñoz-Torres. 2020. "Microfinance Institutions Fostering Sustainable Development by Region" *Sustainability* 12, no. 7: 2682. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12072682>
- Gatto, A. (2021) *Rimesse degli emigranti italiani negli USA, sviluppo e cicli economici: dalle fonti archivistiche del Banco di Napoli ai dati della Banca Mondiale (1861-2017)*. *RiMe. Rivista dell’Istituto di Storia dell’Europa Mediterranea*.
- Gatto, A., Sadik-Zada, E.R. (2022) *Access to microfinance as a resilience policy to address sustainable development goals: A content analysis*. *Heliyon*.

- Hermes N., Lensink R. (2011) Microfinance: Its Impact, Outreach, and Sustainability. *World Development* Vol. 39, No. 6, pp. 875–881.
- Klapper, L., El-Zoghbi, M., and Hess, J. (2016) Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. The Role of Financial Inclusion. UNSGSA, United Nations Secretary General’s Special Advocate for Inclusive Finance for Development.
- Lacalle-Calderon M., Larrù J. M., Garrido S.R., Perez-Trujillo M. (2019) Microfinance and income inequality: New macro-level evidence. *Review of Development Economics*, pp. 860-876.
- Manpreet, A., Swati, S. (2022) Microfinance and Sustainable Development in Africa. IGI GLOBAL Publishing *Tomorrow’s Research Today*, pp. 26.
- Massaro, M., Dumay, J.C. and Guthrie, J. (2016), “On the shoulders of giants: Undertaking a structured literature review in accounting”, *Accounting, Auditing and Accountability Journal*, Vol. 29 No. 5, pp. 767–901.
- Milgram, B. Lynne. “Operationalizing Microfinance: Women and Craftwork in Ifugao, Upland Philippines.” *Human Organization* 60, no. 3 (2001): 212–24. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/44127259>.
- Montgomery, Heather & Weiss, John. (2011). Can Commercially-oriented Microfinance Help Meet the Millennium Development Goals? Evidence from Pakistan. *World Development*. 39. 87-109. 10.1016/j.worlddev.2010.09.001.
- Niels Hermes, Robert Lensink, Aljar Meesters, Outreach and Efficiency of Microfinance Institutions, *World Development*, Volume 39, Issue 6, 2011, Pages 938-948, ISSN 0305-750X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2009.10.018>.
- Raza, Wahid & Ihsan, Anjum & Kakakhel, Shahid. (2023). Role of Microfinance in poverty alleviation in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan (Case Study of District Karak). *Journal of Business & Tourism*. 8. 10-21. 10.34260/jbt.v8i1.240.
- Snyder, H. (2019). Literature review as a research methodology: An overview and guidelines, *Journal of Business Research*, Volume 104, Pages 333-339, ISSN 0148-2963, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.07.039>.
- Tavanti, Marco. “Before Microfinance: The Social Value of Microsavings in Vincentian Poverty Reduction.” *Journal of Business Ethics* 112, no. 4 (2013): 697–706. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23433677>.
- Tilahun Aemiro Tehulu, 2021. "What drives microfinance institution lending behavior? Empirical evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa," *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, Emerald Group Publishing Limited, vol. 18(8), pages 1745-1765, July.
- Tonia Warnecke (2015) “Greening” Gender Equity: Microfinance and the Sustainable Development Agenda, *Journal of Economic Issues*, 49:2, 553-562, DOI: 10.1080/00213624.2015.1042803
- Tranfield, D., Denyer, D. and Smart, P. (2003), Towards a Methodology for Developing Evidence- Informed Management Knowledge by Means of Systematic Review. *British Journal of Management*, 14: 207-222. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8551.00375>
- United Nations (2015). *Transforming Our World: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*.
- Yadav, P.D. & Verma, A.. (2017). Microfinance: Driving empowerment of women. *International Journal of Economic Research*. 14. 439-452.